

Computational Game Unit Balancing based on Game Theory

Emre Önal

(Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Ankara, Türkiye)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6703-9143>, emrek1@gmail.com)

Abdullah Bülbül

(Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Ankara, Türkiye)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2527-2729>, mabulbul@aybu.edu.tr)

Abstract: Optimizing game elements through iterative human playtests can be time-consuming and insufficient for games with complex intransitive mechanics. Imbalances in games often require the release of numerous balance patches. We present a computational method for making each game unit equally preferable against a uniform play strategy. We leverage concepts from game theory to model intricate relationships among intransitive entities. Matching units against each other is modeled as a symmetric zero-sum game, where unit selection represents a strategy and the error is quantified using payoff values derived from unit parameters. The algorithm takes the initial unit parameters provided by the game designer and optimizes them with minimal changes using gradient descent. Consequently, the payoff matrix converges to a state where a uniform strategy is a near Nash equilibrium, ensuring that each unit is equally preferable under the optimized condition. We implemented a testing environment based on fictitious play and verified our results on different scenarios. While the majority of game theory research focuses on finding optimal strategies given specific environmental conditions, this paper takes a different perspective within the context of game design. We explore game theoretic concepts to address the goal of designing environments that lead to desired strategy choices.

Keywords: Game balance, game theory, Nash equilibrium, parameter optimization, gradient descent ascent

Categories: L.5, I.2.8, I.6.3, F.m

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1 Introduction

During the development of a game, balancing the parameters of game elements is not something a designer can determine all at once. Often, designers do not have clear mathematical models readily available to optimize these parameters. After creating a playable prototype, the game undergoes multiple playtests and the designer frequently needs to iteratively optimize the parameters based on the test results. This process presents various challenges. Firstly, it is time-consuming and costly. Additionally, due to human limitations such as fatigue and subjectivity, there is no guarantee that the results will be satisfactory. Parameters unrelated to the core mechanics of the game may tolerate coarse adjustments, but unit or character powers in competitive fighting games are not forgiving of imbalances. Human playtesting may be enough up to a level for games with simple mechanics. However, it is a more challenging task to optimize units

with complicated relations. Games such as StarCraft II and League of Legends have released numerous balance patches since their initial release, indicating that extensive testing during development is not always enough to identify all imbalances. Although not classified as a technical bug, substantial imbalances in game mechanics can exert adverse effects on gameplay, akin to the impact of a bug. When an advantageous strategy is discovered, players tend to favor that strategy, causing other elements to become less engaging. This detracts from the intended gameplay experience the designer aimed to establish with all the game's elements. This study is an attempt to provide a computational method to eliminate imbalances among game units in competitive games with fighting mechanisms.

When the relationships between different elements are defined by a single metric, it is referred to as a transitive relationship. In other words, if B is better than A, and C is better than B, then C is better than A. In contrast, in an intransitive relationship, such an obligation does not exist. A well-known example of an intransitive game is rock-paper-scissors. In games that employ a transitive power model, balance is often achieved by maintaining a constant ratio between cost and power. Powerful items or units should be more expensive compared to weaker elements. Maintaining balance in such scenarios is relatively straightforward, however, designers may resort to intransitive mechanics to enhance gameplay experience and provide more engaging decision-making options [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a, Morris and Rollings, 2004].

Intransitive mechanics can be found in combat units in real-time strategy (RTS) games, characters in fighting games and Multiplayer Online Battle Arena (MOBA) games, character classes in Massively Multiplayer Online (MMO) games, decks and strategies in trading card games, and more. An example of such a relationship can be observed in an older game called The Ancient Art of War, where the three fighting units - knights, barbarians, and archers - exhibit clear examples of this type of relationship. Barbarians are fast units that can close in on archers with minimal damage, but they are weaker than knights. Knights, on the other hand, are slow but powerful units, which puts them at a disadvantage against archers. As a result, each unit has an advantage over one unit and a disadvantage against another. Fighting games like Street Fighter and Mortal Kombat also feature similar relationships in their mechanics. Attacks are countered by blocks, blocks are countered by throws and throw attempts are countered by attacks. In many RTS games, such as the Warcraft series, aerial units beat infantry units, infantry beat ranged units, and ranged units beat aerial units.

The complicated relationships among game entities in an intransitive mechanics setting make it challenging to adjust their parameters to achieve the desired outcome. Some examples of this are mentioned in Section 4. The strategically interdependent behavior of different entities in such scenarios has been extensively studied in game theory. Game theory encompasses a wide range of areas, including economics, biology, politics, psychology, and more, where various problems are modeled as games and analyzed. In our case, unit or character selection can be viewed as a metagame akin to rock-paper-scissors where players choose their strategy among game units instead of rock, paper, or scissors. Then the selected units confront each other. The outcome of these confrontations is determined by the power differences between the units. In game theory terminology, the outcome of the game for each player is referred to as a *payoff*, and the term *strategy* is used to define a player's plan of action, which, in our case, corresponds to the unit or character selection. In game theory, payoff matrices are used to express the outcomes of players' strategy choices. It is like an abstract model of a game. Figure 1b shows a payoff matrix for rock-paper-scissors game.

Topics of game theory cover finding optimal player strategies under given circum-

stances. Nash equilibrium refers to a set of strategies, one for each player, where each player's choice represents the best response to the strategies of other players. In other words, no player can benefit from changing their strategy given the current state. We mentioned a few examples of intransitive relationships above, where a single (pure) best strategy does not exist. No matter which strategy (game unit, or fight move) a player chooses, the opponent can choose a better counter strategy. In such cases, the optimal strategy a player can have is to choose according to a probability distribution over multiple strategies. This is called a mixed strategy. In a rock-paper-scissors game, the optimal strategy is to play each element with a probability of $1/3$. The mixed strategy where each pure strategy is selected with an equally distributed probability like this can be called a uniform strategy [Maubert and Pinchinat, 2014]. According to the Nash theorem, all finite games have at least one Nash equilibrium, whether composed of mixed or pure strategies. However, computing an exact Nash equilibrium is a tricky subject. In many cases, a solution called a near-Nash equilibrium or epsilon-equilibrium, which refers to a solution very close to the Nash equilibrium, is preferred.

This study aims to provide a computational solution to balance game unit/character powers. In the academic literature, the term *game balance* is used in different forms depending on the problems addressed. Becker and Görlich analyzed fourteen authors' concepts of game balancing [Becker and Görlich, 2020] and concluded that although they agree on certain aspects, there is no central goal of balancing among them. One thing they all agree on is that games should provide meaningful decision options to the players. If one thing is always at a disadvantage against others, that option becomes pointless. In this study, we define our balancing goal as each game unit being equally preferable against a uniform opponent strategy. We utilize concepts from game theory to detect imbalances and quantify the error based on unit parameters. We then optimize unit parameters with gradient descent to minimize the error.

Game theory has a wide range of applications in different kinds of disciplines. A common problem researchers work with in game theory is finding optimum strategies under certain conditions. Examples of this are mentioned in Section 1.1. In a game design context, the structure of the problem turns into designing an ideal gaming environment that will favor a balanced strategy. Here the strategy distribution becomes an input to the problem. The game unit parameters, which are used to construct payoff values, are optimized in a way to make a uniform strategy set a Nash equilibrium. Details of the algorithm are explained in Section 3.

1.1 Related Works

Game balancing is a multifaceted research area. Different aspects of it are covered in various studies [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a, Beau and Bakkes, 2016, Morosan and Poli, 2017, DeLaurentis et al., 2021, Jaffe, 2013, Beyer et al., 2016, Becker and Görlich, 2020]. There is no standardized technique to handle balancing in games. Balancing the game manually based on observations from human playtests is a common practice in the gaming industry. However, this approach has several drawbacks, which have been discussed in different studies. Zook et al. [Zook et al., 2019] focus on updating the game parameter set more efficiently by using active learning. They speed up the testing process by reducing the number of playtests. Other studies try to remove human playtests at all and use AI agents instead. Bergdahl et al. [Bergdahl et al., 2020] use a deep reinforcement learning agent to find exploits, test map difficulty, and detect common problems that arise during gameplay. Gudmundsson et al. [Gudmundsson et al., 2018] use a convolutional

	Rock	Paper	Scissors
Rock	1	0	2
Paper	2	1	0
Scissor	0	2	1

P1\P2	Rock	Paper	Scissors
Rock	(0,0)	(-2,2)	(2,-2)
Paper	(2,-2)	(0,0)	(-2,2)
Scissor	(-2,2)	(2,-2)	(0,0)

(a) The values in the cells represent the power of the row unit against the column unit.

(b) Payoff matrices for player1 and player2 colored by red and blue respectively.

Figure 1: An intransitive power model defined on a power table (a) for a rock-paper-scissors game scenario and the payoff matrices (b) derived from the power table by taking the power difference of the confronting units against each other.

neural network-based agent trained on human-player data to estimate the difficulty level in match-3 games.

The optimization and tuning process of game parameters constitute a more focused research area. A group of approaches in this field are interested in tuning game parameters regarding game-playing agents [Patel et al., 2011, Kocsis and Szepesvari, 2006, Sironi and Winands, 2017]. However, the aspect of interest in our study is not optimizing the agent behaviour but rather parameter tuning to balance game elements. There are relatively fewer studies in this particular line of research. Quinones et al. [Quinones and Fernández, 2022] proposed an automated solution for parameter optimization by conducting a hill-climbing search around different selected parameter sets. The value of each parameter set is evaluated by executing the game with those parameters. Wang and Zhang [Wang and Zhang, 2021] balance combat units with transitive mechanics by minimizing the deviations of damage and loss values. They use an evolutionary algorithm to find optimization solutions.

The concept of intransitivity became the subject of interdisciplinary discussions after the studies of Gardner [Gardner, 1970, Gardner, 1974]. Intransitivity is also utilized by game designers to provide more engaging gameplay. Some examples of games using these mechanics are mentioned in Section 1. The engaging interaction provided by intransitive mechanics comes with the price of design complexity [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a, Morris and Rollings, 2004]. The balance between the elements of a transitive game can be achieved simply by keeping the ratio between costs and benefits constant [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a]. When it comes to complex interactions among intransitive game elements, concepts from game theory are used to analyze those relations [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a, Morris and Rollings, 2004]. Jaffe provides a detailed example of this in his analysis of Street Fighter 4 [Jaffe, 2013]. He uses the community-built matchup tier list as a 39x39 power table shown in Figure 2 and creates the payoff matrix from this power table the same way we do. The entries in the table are the win rate out of ten games. He defines the balance meant by the players in this game exactly the way we define balance in our study. His studies are also only concerned with understanding the balance. We haven't encountered any study providing a computational solution for balancing game parameters in an intransitive environment.

Game theory is actively used for parameter optimization problems. A common approach is to model a problem as a game and update the probability distributions of the mixed strategies of the players using different techniques to converge to a Nash equilibrium [Meng et al., 2010, Cheng and Liu, 2020]. As one of many examples, Moolchandani et al. [Moolchandani et al., 2021] model the path planning problem of an unmanned aerial

	S	V	C	A	F	R	S	B	A	I	A	B	M	B	R	K	Y	Z	D	G	S	C	D	J	R	G	G	C	F	Y	H	G	V	D	O	E	H	T	D	T		
Seth	-	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	6	6	5	5	6	7	6	6	4	6	5	6	6	6	4	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	7	206
C. Viper	6	-	6	6	5	5	4	5	4	6	5	6	4	6	6	5	4	7	6	5	6	4	6	6	5	6	5	5	5	6	5	5	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	205	
Cammy	6	4	-	6	4	5	6	4	5	6	6	6	4	6	5	5	4	6	4	5	5	4	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	205	
Akuma	5	4	4	-	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	6	6	6	6	5	5	6	6	5	5	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	204		
F. Ling	6	5	6	5	-	5	6	4	5	5	6	5	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	6	4	5	5	5	6	5	5	6	5	5	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	203		
Rufus	5	5	5	5	-	4	5	5	6	6	5	6	5	4	5	6	3	6	4	6	6	4	5	7	4	4	5	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	5	7	200				
Sagat	5	4	4	4	6	-	6	5	4	5	5	5	6	6	7	5	5	6	4	5	4	6	5	4	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	4	6	6	6	6	6	6	200			
Balrog	5	6	6	5	6	5	-	6	5	5	6	6	5	5	5	4	4	4	6	4	5	5	6	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	5	5	5	6	5	5	198			
Adon	6	5	5	5	5	4	-	5	6	5	6	5	6	5	5	4	6	6	5	5	6	6	5	5	6	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	4	6	195					
Ibuki	5	6	4	5	4	6	5	-	5	4	5	5	5	4	6	6	5	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6	4	6	195				
Abel	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	-	6	5	6	5	4	7	6	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6	6	6	4	5	6	6	4	5	194						
Blanka	5	5	4	5	5	4	6	4	-	5	4	5	5	6	4	6	5	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	4	5	4	5	5	4	8	6	194									
Makoto	5	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	-	5	5	5	4	6	6	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	5	4	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	194				
Bison	4	6	6	5	5	5	6	5	5	-	5	4	4	3	6	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	194				
Ryu	4	4	4	5	4	6	5	4	5	4	5	5	-	5	6	4	5	6	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	194				
Ken	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	-	6	5	4	4	5	6	6	4	5	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	193				
Yun	4	5	6	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	6	4	4	-	4	7	6	5	6	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	193				
Zangief	3	6	6	4	4	7	3	6	6	6	4	6	6	4	5	-	4	4	5	3	4	4	4	4	4	7	6	5	5	4	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	193				
Dhalsim	4	3	4	4	4	5	6	6	4	3	6	4	5	6	6	3	6	-	6	4	6	4	5	6	6	5	4	7	5	5	6	5	6	5	6	7	192					
Guile	4	4	6	4	5	6	6	4	4	4	4	7	5	6	4	6	4	-	5	6	5	6	4	5	4	5	6	5	5	5	6	5	6	5	6	7	192					
Sakura	5	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	6	5	-	5	6	5	6	5	5	4	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	192				
Chun-Li	4	4	5	4	4	6	6	5	5	6	5	5	4	4	7	4	4	-	5	5	5	5	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	191				
Dee Jay	5	5	6	4	6	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	6	4	5	-	5	4	5	5	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	191				
Juri	4	6	4	5	4	5	5	6	4	5	4	5	5	6	4	4	5	-	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	191				
Rose	4	4	4	5	6	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	6	6	4	6	5	5	-	6	6	5	6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	190				
Gouken	4	4	4	4	5	6	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	6	6	4	5	4	5	-	4	4	6	6	5	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	189				
Guy	6	5	5	4	5	6	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	4	6	-	4	5	5	5	5	6	6	4	4	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	189					
Cody	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	6	-	4	4	5	5	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	188					
Fuente	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	5	4	-	5	6	4	4	4	5	6	6	5	6	5	5	5	5	187						
Yang	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	6	5	5	4	5	4	6	5	5	4	6	6	4	-	6	6	4	4	6	4	6	4	6	4	6	4	6	4	6	187				
Honda	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	6	5	4	5	6	4	5	4	5	3	4	6	4	6	6	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	186					
Geh	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	6	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	-	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	185					
Vega	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	6	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	183					
Dudley	4	5	5	5	6	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	-	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	182					
Oni	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	176					
Evil Ryu	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	175					
Hakan	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	169					
T. Hawk	3	4	4	4	4	5	3	5	6	6	2	4	5	4	5	6	5	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	166					
Dan	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	148					

Figure 2: Eventhubs Community Tier List for Street Fighter 4. The entries show the win rates out of ten games. Units are ordered according to the total table score. [Goldsberry, 2012]

vehicle as a game and calculate the Nash equilibrium using a software tool called Gambit, developed for game theory related computations. Then, the strategies are mapped to the optimal values of the tunable parameters. As mentioned at the end of Section 1, most of the game theory studies focus on updating player strategies based on environmental conditions. We encountered very few studies that make modifications to the payoff values [Worden and Levin, 2007, Akçay and Roughgarden, 2011]. In a game design context, the environment becomes an input to modify. In our study, we work in that direction.

2 Problem Definition

In games featuring intransitive mechanics, the presence of imbalances among game units or characters may not be immediately apparent. However, as players invest hours into gameplay and explore various combinations, these imbalances which make some of them redundant or more advantageous can become evident. This poses a challenge for competitive games, as they often need to release multiple balance patches after the initial release to address these issues. The industry currently lacks standardized computational solutions for handling intransitive elements.

In our study, we defined our goal as each game unit being equally preferable against a uniform opponent strategy. This also means modifying game parameters in a way

that will make a uniform strategy set a Nash equilibrium for the game. In the scenario of our methodology, initial power parameters decided by the designer are given to the algorithm in a power table, and our method balances the game units with the smallest changes to the given parameter set. An example representation of each confrontation in a rock-paper-scissors game is shown in the payoff matrix in Figure 1b. The values in payoff matrices are derived from the power differences of the corresponding units defined in the power table in Figure 1a. To calculate the payoff value of the game when the players choose a mixed strategy, the payoff value of each cell is multiplied by the probability of that cell, then all the values are summed. The probability of each cell is calculated by multiplying the strategy probabilities of players corresponding to that cell. We calculate the payoff value of the game where player1 chooses a pure strategy, which is selecting a single row unit with a probability of 1, against a uniform strategy played by player2. We use this payoff value as an error indicating how balanced the unit chosen by player1 is. The game is balanced if the payoffs for all units are zero. In addition to detecting an imbalance, quantifying the error opens up the way to efficient parameter updating. As the objective function, we minimize the sum of the squared payoffs of all units using gradient descent. As a result, we balance the game with the minimal possible changes to the given initial parameter set.

We define our game unit optimization problem as a mini-game where each of the two players chooses a unit with a unique power profile to confront each other, as shown in Figure 1. The power difference between the units is used as the payoff value. This game fits the description of a two-player symmetric zero-sum game. It is symmetric because the game units work the same way regardless of the player using them. During a clash between two units, the power difference will affect one player positively and the other negatively, resulting in a total payoff of zero for the two players. This makes it a zero-sum game.

When we observe a row in a payoff matrix as in Figure 1b, we see that a unit can be strong or weak against different units. This is something desired to provide diverse strategies in a game. But at the same time, we want each unit to be equally valuable in an overall evaluation against all units. In our scenario when the player2 (column selector) plays with a uniform strategy, the payoff value for each pure strategy of player1 (row selector) indicates how advantageous that row unit is against all units on average. That payoff value acts as an error for balance. As an ideal example in the payoff matrix in Figure 1b we see that the payoff value for each row selection against a uniform column selection is zero.

We can modify the payoff value indirectly by modifying the power parameters in the power table. However, changing a power parameter affects two symmetric entries in the payoff matrix. So we can not optimize each row of the payoff matrix independently. When all this is considered we define our optimization problem as minimizing the squared sums of the row payoffs against a uniform strategy of column selector (player2). We optimize with gradient descent to achieve the balance with minimal modification.

3 Methodology

For ease of expression, player1 (row selector) and player2 (column selector) will be referred to as attacker and defender respectively. The payoff to the attacker in a confrontation is calculated by subtracting the defense power from the attack power. In a game played with a mixed strategy, the influence of multiple entries in the power table will be weighted according to the probability distributions of the players' strategies. We

Figure 3: Attack(b), defense(c), and weight(d) matrices for a strategy set(a) where the defender chooses each strategy by prob. dist. 1/3 and the attacker chooses rock by prob. dist. 1 in a rock-paper-scissors game. The weight matrix is calculated by subtracting the defense matrix from the attack matrix.

build an attack and defense matrix to represent those weights. The power table gives the power of row units against column units. So to obtain the power of defense units against attack units, we transpose the attack matrix. A final weight matrix is obtained by subtracting the defense matrix from the attack matrix in Eq. 1 where i is the index of the attacker's strategy choice. This weight matrix is used to create payoff values from the power table. In Figure 3 these matrices are displayed for the case when the attacker chooses the first row against the defender who plays a uniform strategy. Each element in the weight matrix expresses the weights of the corresponding entry in the power table on the payoff. According to Figure 3d, entries (1,2) and (1,3) have a positive effect, while entries (2,1) and (3,1) have a negative effect at the same magnitude. The other entries have no effect. That means changing those values in the power table will not change the payoff matrix. Therefore, it will not affect the outcome.

In the next step in Eq. 2, where m is the number of strategies, we sum the entries of the element-wise multiplication of the weight matrix and power table (mentioned as the power matrix in the equation) to find the payoff value of the game. This payoff value corresponds to the error for the selected row unit, and the weight matrix contains the mapping information to the power table that is responsible for this error. In other words, the weight matrix gives information on how to distribute the required change over the power table. So the product of the weight matrix and the payoff value gives us a gradient matrix to update the values in the power table. We multiply the weight matrix and the payoff values for each row unit and add them up to calculate a total gradient matrix in Eq. 3 (We dropped the constant 2 obtained from the derivative of the square.). In the last step, the gradient matrix is multiplied with a small learning rate, which is denoted as α in Eq. 4, and the power table is updated with it. At each iteration, the sum of the squared errors is measured and execution is stopped when it drops below a certain threshold. Other types of convergence methods can be applied here. If we analogize this process to a training step in a single-layered neural network, payoff values are the errors in the output nodes, and the unit power parameters are updated in this process, similar to how the weight parameters in the neural network are updated.

$$WeightMatrix_i = AttackMatrix_i - DefenseMatrix_i \quad (1)$$

$$payoff_i = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^m (WeightMatrix_i \odot PowerMatrix_i)_{jk} \quad (2)$$

$$GradientMatrix = \sum_{i=1}^m (WeightMatrix_i * payoff_i) \quad (3)$$

$$PowerMatrix \rightarrow PowerMatrix - \alpha * GradientMatrix \quad (4)$$

4 Experiments and Discussion

4.1 Test Environment

Fictitious play [Brown, 1951] is a learning strategy initially proposed as a method for computing Nash equilibrium. It is inspired by the ways that people would learn to play a game. In fictitious play, each player selects their best response against the estimated strategy of the opponent. In finite zero-sum games, fictitious play converges to a Nash equilibrium [Robinson, 1951], although it should be noted that a game may have multiple Nash equilibria.

We developed a testing environment inspired by the concept of fictitious play. The strategies of players are equal in the Nash equilibrium of symmetric zero-sum games. There is no need to search for separate strategies for different players. We run a simulation where the game is played multiple rounds at each iteration. Player1 starts with an initial strategy and he is opposed by all pure strategies. At the end of each iteration, player1 modifies his strategy to improve his performance against his opponent's best strategy. Here again, we used gradient descent for optimization. This time the payoffs remain constant, and the strategy probabilities are optimized. In the end, the game with the optimized parameters reaches a near Nash equilibrium.

It should be noted that in an environment with a limited number of players and slow information exchange, the players' strategies may not converge to a Nash equilibrium quickly, but as long as the players act rationally, the change should be in that direction.

4.2 Three Units

In a rock-paper-scissors game with an ideal payoff matrix, the Nash equilibrium is equally distributed. When player1 starts with a random distribution in Figure 4 we see it converges to a uniform strategy in time, as expected.

In a game, ideal playing strategy may not be understood from the mere appearance of a power table filled with random values. The payoff matrix gives a better understanding since it shows the outcomes of each matching. A game designed with the power table in Figure 5 favors the scissors. The payoff matrix reveals that there is no matching where the scissors are at a loss. It is expected that the strategy to converge to a pure scissors strategy, which is confirmed by the graph.

We optimized the power table in Figure 5 according to our algorithm. The resulting power table, payoff matrix, and the simulation graph are shown in Figure 6. It shows the

Figure 4: A rock-paper-scissors game is designed with an ideal power profile as defined in (b). The simulation starts with a random initial strategy (e.g., 0.2 : 0.1 : 0.7 in the graph) and converges to a uniform strategy.

Figure 5: The game is designed with random power parameters. The scissors have an advantage in this set of parameters, as can be seen in the payoff matrix. The simulation starts with a random initial strategy (0.2 : 0.1 : 0.7 in the graph) and converges to 0:0:1 which is a pure scissors strategy.

same pattern as Figure 4 and converges to a uniform strategy. Since the optimization is performed with gradient descent, the parameters in the diagonal entries are not changed. Because the change in those parameters does not affect the outcome of the game.

By making a small modification to the simple power model described for rock-paper-scissors in Figure 4 and increasing the power of the rock against the scissors from 2 to 4, as shown in Figure 7 we begin to see the complicated behavior of intransitive relations. Despite having the highest total payoff value against all units, rock is not the most preferred option. Paper becomes the highest strategy by 0.5, and the others become 0.25. The initial instinct would be to select rock more frequently and scissors less frequently. However, this creates a perfect environment for paper. A mathematical solution that supports these results can be found [Schreiber and Romero, 2021b]. This implies that the balance problem we are working on can not be easily addressed by intuitively modifying the values in a payoff table.

Figure 6: The power table is optimized with our algorithm and the game is played with the payoff values derived from the optimized power table. The simulation starts with a random initial strategy (0.2 : 0.1 : 0.7 in the graph) and converges to a uniform strategy.

Figure 7: Ideal power profile for rock-paper-scissors is modified. The power of rock against scissors is increased (*).

Figure 8: 5 units with unoptimized power table. The simulation is started with a uniform strategy.

4.3 Multiple Units

As mentioned earlier, a game may have multiple Nash equilibria. Fictitious play may converge differently depending on the initial strategies, but we expect the strategies not to change when the simulation is started from a Nash equilibrium. In Figure 8,

Figure 9: 5 units with optimized power table. The simulation is started with a uniform strategy.

random initial values are entered into the power table of a game with 5 units. When the simulation starts with a uniform distribution, since the game is not balanced yet, the strategies diverge from the initial condition and converge to a Nash equilibrium in which the strategy probabilities of two units are zero. This indicates that those two units have become redundant in this Nash equilibrium.

When we optimize the power values, as shown in Figure 9, the strategy distribution remains the same throughout the simulation, indicating that a uniform strategy is a Nash equilibrium for the new game with the optimized power parameters.

Figure 10: 5 units with optimized power table. The simulation is started with a different initial strategy (0.6 : 0.2 : 0.05 : 0.05 : 0.1 in the graph). It converges to a different Nash equilibrium.

When the optimized game in Figure 9 started from a different initial strategy, it converged to a different Nash equilibrium than the uniform strategy. This is shown in Figure 10. However, when we designed a game with 3 optimized units, the simulations always converged to the same strategy, regardless of the initial strategy, as seen in Figure 6.

The results presented in Figure 11 are the same tests conducted in Figure 8 and 9 with a larger number of units. Both tests exhibit similar characteristics, albeit taking longer

Figure 11: 50 units with unoptimized (left) and optimized (right) power table. The simulation is started with a uniform strategy.

to complete. The optimization process in both cases is completed in under a second, as indicated in Table 1.

	Optimization	Simulation
5 units	89 ms	1627 ms
50 units	742 ms	10231 ms

Table 1: Optimization and simulation times of tests performed with 5 and 50 units. The algorithm is implemented in Python and tested on a Windows 10 machine with AMD Ryzen 5 5600x processor.

4.4 Street Fighter Characters

Figure 12: 39 units from Street Fighter 4 with unoptimized (left) and optimized (right) power table. The simulation is started with a uniform strategy.

Furthermore, we applied our method on Street Fighter 4 characters, using the community tier list in Figure 2 as a power table, which is also used in the same way in Jaffe's work [Jaffe, 2013]. An example of the situation experienced in Figure 7 exists here

among a larger unit set. On the left graph in Figure 12 where we used the power table directly as provided in Figure 2, the unit with the highest selection rate is Balrog with 0.27, shown by a gray line, followed by Akuma with 0.16, shown by a red line. They are ranked 8th and 4th respectively on the tier list. Although they are in the top tier, they are not 1st and 2nd. Similarly, Jaffe also reports Balrog as a dominant force of the game in different Nash equilibria he found. The simulation result with the optimized power table is shown on the right graph. This graph means that each unit is equally preferable in the optimized game when all of the character relations are considered.

Here the power parameters in the initial power table are the win rates of players which is not something to configure directly, but they are an indication of how advantageous a character is in each confrontation. The updates to these parameters in the optimized results can guide the modifications to adjust the character relations. For instance, if the power parameters (win rates) of an imbalanced pair, such as a pair with a 3 to 7 win rate against each other, remain unchanged after optimization, it implies that there is no need to intervene in the power relation between those two characters. Conversely, in certain cases, breaking a tie in a balanced pair with a 5 to 5 odds of winning against each other can enhance the overall game balance.

For a scenario in which a character in a fighting game competes against all other characters one by one in a tournament, the problem is to balance each unit against an equally distributed strategy, which is the exact solution provided in our study. In a more flexible scenario, such as a strategy game where armies composed of varying amounts of different soldier units battle each other, a more generic problem definition is required. We mentioned earlier that Becker and Görlich [Becker and Görlich, 2020] stated "providing meaningful decision options" as a commonly accepted concept in game balancing. This concept, which entails each unit being a valuable selection in some strategy, can be employed as a design consideration from a game design perspective. If a unit can be profitably replaced by another unit in all possible strategies, then that unit becomes useless. This issue can be solved by designing a game that has a Nash equilibrium that incorporates this unit. In the examples given so far, we demonstrate that the algorithm can optimize unit parameters to achieve a uniform Nash equilibrium that encompasses all units.

4.5 Custom Strategy Distribution

Figure 13: A rock-paper-scissors game designed to have a specified (0.5 : 0.3 : 0.2) Nash equilibrium. The simulation starts with a random initial strategy (0.1 : 0.1 : 0.8 in the graph) and converges to the desired strategy (0.5 : 0.3 : 0.2).

While a uniform strategy selection is not necessarily a requirement in a more flexible scenario, if the designer requires it for game-specific reasons, the algorithm allows a uniform or any other Nash equilibrium in the final optimized parameter set. The power table presented in Figure 5 is optimized to have a game with a Nash equilibrium using a specified strategy distribution of (0.5 : 0.3 : 0.2). In the optimization step if we assign this specified strategy to player2 instead of a uniform strategy, the simulation conducted on this game converges to the given strategy. The simulation result is depicted in Figure 13.

5 Use Cases

This methodology can be applied to different types of games and may need modifications based on specific design requirements. In this section, we briefly discuss some considerations for its application.

In strategy games, there is a progression of soldier units that players can create. Elite units, which can be created towards the end of the game, may cost more resources and tend to be more powerful. The values assigned to the power table can be normalized based on the creation cost of each unit. By normalizing the values, we can effectively compare the relative power levels of different units, taking into account their resource investment.

If the designer intentionally wants to favor a unit in terms of power, he can play with the cost-power relation in the normalization step. However, if the goal is to increase the utilization of a unit in the game, it is important to remember that simply strengthening that unit does not necessarily mean that it will be preferred more. This is discussed in Section 4 on Figure 7. Fortunately, the unit selection preference is directly adjustable in our algorithm. The strategy used for player2 in the optimization step is exactly the strategy that the Nash equilibrium is built up to. In the last example we gave in Section 4 a power configuration optimized to have a Nash equilibrium with the strategy of 0.5 : 0.3 : 0.2 instead of a uniform strategy.

In certain scenarios, game designers may have the requirement to maintain specific parameters unchanged during the optimization process. For example, when introducing a new character to the game, the designer may wish to preserve the existing parameters without modification. To address this need, a selector matrix can be created, aligning with the entries in the power table. By assigning ones and zeros to the corresponding entries, the selector matrix acts as a control mechanism. During the update step, the gradient matrix can be multiplied element-wise with the selector matrix. This operation ensures that elements in the power table associated with entries marked as zeros in the selector matrix remain unaltered. In this way, the designer retains control over which parameters undergo modification during the optimization process. Furthermore, by assigning values other than 0 and 1 in the selector matrix, the designer can fine-tune the extent of parameter changes on an individual basis.

In strategy games, units often exhibit varying strengths against different unit classes rather than individual unit types. To demonstrate this concept in a strategy game context, we implemented an illustrative example. We considered a scenario where the game designer categorizes fighting units into three distinct classes: infantry, ranged, and mounted units. Each unit in the game has three distinct power parameters that determine its effectiveness against these three classes. Instead of assigning separate power values for each individual unit type, as outlined in the core algorithm template, we introduced a class-specific mapping table for each soldier unit. This mapping table contains the class

	infantry	ranged	mounted
infantry1	350	200	800
infantry2	500	300	700
infantry3	550	350	650
ranged1	850	500	200
ranged2	700	600	300
mounted1	350	700	400
mounted2	400	900	550

Table 2: Initial power parameters entered by the designer. Each entry shows the power of the row soldier unit against the column soldier class.

	infantry	ranged	mounted
infantry1	411	280	861
infantry2	482	327	708
infantry3	505	360	640
ranged1	786	497	177
ranged2	644	602	283
mounted1	394	769	449
mounted2	294	869	500

Table 3: Power parameters optimized by the algorithm. Results are rounded to integer. ($\epsilon = 0.01$)

information, which is utilized to determine the corresponding power parameter during the calculation process. The game designer’s objective is to establish an intransitive power model, where infantry beats mounted, mounted beats ranged, and ranged beats infantry. To achieve this, seven soldier units are defined, each with power parameters calibrated to reflect this intransitive relationship. Tables 2 and 3 present the initial and optimized power parameter sets, respectively, for the seven soldier units. Each row in the tables corresponds to a unique soldier unit, with its power values against infantry, ranged, and mounted units listed in the respective columns. The initial and optimized payoff matrices are illustrated in Figure 14, where blue and red regions denote the desired outcomes based on the intransitive relationship between soldier classes. Specifically, blue cells indicate that the row unit is expected to defeat the column unit, whereas red cells indicate the opposite. Consequently, the payoff values in blue cells should be positive, while those in red cells should be negative. The gradient descent algorithm yields results with the minimum possible change. In this example, we observe that the desired intransitive superiority is preserved during optimization. Furthermore, the game designer can intervene in the optimization process by utilizing a selection matrix to refine the results.

6 Conclusion & Future Work

In this study, we have presented a computational solution for balancing units in games that utilize parametric values in their fighting mechanisms. The proposed algorithm takes

	infantry1	infantry2	infantry3	ranged1	ranged2	mounted1	mounted2		infantry1	infantry2	infantry3	ranged1	ranged2	mounted1	mounted2
infantry1	0	-150	-200	-650	-500	450	400	infantry1	0	-70	-94	-505	-364	466	566
infantry2	150	0	-50	-550	-400	350	300	infantry2	70	0	-23	-458	-316	314	414
infantry3	200	50	0	-500	-350	300	250	infantry3	94	23	0	-425	-284	246	346
ranged1	650	550	500	0	-100	-500	-700	ranged1	505	458	425	0	-105	-591	-691
ranged2	500	400	350	100	0	-400	-600	ranged2	364	316	284	105	0	-485	-585
mounted1	-450	-350	-300	500	400	0	-150	mounted1	-466	-314	-246	591	485	0	-50
mounted2	-400	-300	-250	700	600	150	0	mounted2	-566	-414	-346	691	585	50	0

Figure 14: Initial (left) and optimized (right) payoff matrices. Blue and red cells indicate encounters where units are expected to be superior and inferior according to intransitive design concerns.

an initial parameter set and optimizes it to achieve a balanced state with minimal changes. We have leveraged concepts from game theory to address the complexities of intransitive relationships in game environments. The imbalance has been detected and quantified by calculating the total payoffs associated with the selection of each game unit against a uniform strategy. In the end, the power parameters are optimized using gradient descent, minimizing the imbalance.

During the game balancing process, the game is typically tested either by human players or AI bots. The test results are then analyzed to identify any imbalances, and based on these evaluations, the game designer makes adjustments to reduce these imbalances. The updated version is subsequently tested again to assess the effectiveness of the changes. Various studies have focused on different aspects of game balancing, providing solutions for different stages of this iterative cycle. Our algorithm addresses all stages of parameter balancing, eliminating the need for human intervention entirely. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the only one that offers a computational solution for parameter balancing in intransitive game environments. Moreover, the computational cost of our algorithm is negligible. In our tests, it successfully optimized 50 unit parameters in under a second. To evaluate and validate our optimization results, we developed a testing environment inspired by fictitious play and conducted experiments in various scenarios. Additionally, our algorithm is flexible and open to modifications to accommodate specific design requirements, as discussed in Section. 5.

In our research, our primary focus has been on games where the power values of characters are defined parametrically. However, as an alternative approach, we can also consider utilizing statistical gameplay data collected from players to construct a power table, similar to the approach taken in Jaffe’s study. This opens up the possibility of using our method to balance units in games where gameplay data can be obtained from the player community. In the presence of successful game-playing AI agents, we can gather valuable information from these agents to fine-tune and balance the game during the development phase before its release. Such applications could serve as compelling case studies.

Furthermore, it would be intriguing to explore the application of this technique in contexts beyond games, where the problem structure aligns with the setting considered in our study. By expanding our scope to other domains, we can assess the effectiveness of our approach in addressing similar challenges.

Statements and Declarations

Ethical Approval

This declaration is not applicable for this study.

Authors' contributions

E.Ö. designed the idea and the algorithm, implemented it, and wrote the main manuscript. A.B. supervised the study and made suggestions, corrections, and additions to the study and the manuscript. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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Availability of data and materials

Source-code for the algorithm and the examples explained in this paper are available at [Onal, 2024]. Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

- [Akçay and Roughgarden, 2011] Akçay, E. and Roughgarden, J. (2011). The evolution of payoff matrices: providing incentives to cooperate. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 278:2198–2206.
- [Beau and Bakkes, 2016] Beau, P. and Bakkes, S. (2016). Automated game balancing of asymmetric video games. In *2016 IEEE conference on computational intelligence and games (CIG)*, pages 1–8. IEEE.
- [Becker and Görlich, 2020] Becker, A. and Görlich, D. (2020). What is game balancing?-an examination of concepts. *ParadigmPlus*, 1(1):22–41.
- [Bergdahl et al., 2020] Bergdahl, J., Gordillo, C., Tollmar, K., and Gisslén, L. (2020). Augmenting automated game testing with deep reinforcement learning. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Games (CoG)*, pages 600–603. IEEE.
- [Beyer et al., 2016] Beyer, M., Agureikin, A., Anokhin, A., Laenger, C., Nolte, F., Winterberg, J., Renka, M., Rieger, M., Pflanzl, N., Preuss, M., and Volz, V. (2016). An integrated process for game balancing. *2016 IEEE Conference on Computational Intelligence and Games (CIG)*, pages 1–8.
- [Brown, 1951] Brown, G. W. (1951). Iterative solution of games by fictitious play. *Act. Anal. Prod Allocation*, 13(1):374.
- [Cheng and Liu, 2020] Cheng, D. and Liu, Z. (2020). Optimization via game theoretic control. *National Science Review*, 7(7):1120–1122.
- [DeLaurentis et al., 2021] DeLaurentis, D. A., Panchal, J. H., Raz, A. K., Balasubramani, P., Maheshwari, A., Dachowicz, A., and Mall, K. (2021). Toward automated game balance: A systematic engineering design approach. In *2021 IEEE Conference on Games (CoG)*, pages 1–8. IEEE.

- [Gardner, 1970] Gardner, M. (1970). The paradox of the nontransitive dice and the elusive principle of indifference. *Scientific American*, 223(6):110–114.
- [Gardner, 1974] Gardner, M. (1974). On the paradoxical situations that arise from nontransitive relations. *Scientific American*, 231(4):120–125.
- [Goldsberry, 2012] Goldsberry, K. (2012). Tiers for super street fighter 4 arcade edition v2012 by the eventhubs community.
- [Gudmundsson et al., 2018] Gudmundsson, S. F., Eisen, P., Poromaa, E., Nodet, A., Purmonen, S., Kozakowski, B., Meurling, R., and Cao, L. (2018). Human-like playtesting with deep learning. In *2018 IEEE Conference on Computational Intelligence and Games (CIG)*, pages 1–8. IEEE.
- [Jaffe, 2013] Jaffe, A. B. (2013). *Understanding game balance with quantitative methods*. PhD thesis.
- [Kocsis and Szepesvari, 2006] Kocsis, L. and Szepesvari, C. (2006). Universal parameter optimisation in games based on spsa. *Machine Learning*, 63:249–286.
- [Maubert and Pinchinat, 2014] Maubert, B. and Pinchinat, S. (2014). A general notion of uniform strategies. *International Game Theory Review*, 16(01):1440004.
- [Meng et al., 2010] Meng, R., Ye, Y., and Xie, N. (2010). Multi-objective optimization design methods based on game theory. *2010 8th World Congress on Intelligent Control and Automation*, pages 2220–2227.
- [Moolchandani et al., 2021] Moolchandani, D., Prathap, G., Afanasyev, I. M., Kumar, A., Mazzara, M., and Sarangi, S. R. (2021). Game theory-based parameter-tuning for path planning of uavs. *2021 34th International Conference on VLSI Design and 2021 20th International Conference on Embedded Systems (VLSID)*, pages 187–192.
- [Morosan and Poli, 2017] Morosan, M. and Poli, R. (2017). Automated game balancing in ms pacman and starcraft using evolutionary algorithms. In *Applications of Evolutionary Computation: 20th European Conference, EvoApplications 2017, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, April 19-21, 2017, Proceedings, Part I 20*, pages 377–392. Springer.
- [Morris and Rollings, 2004] Morris, D. and Rollings, A. (2004). *Game architecture and design*. a new edition.
- [Onal, 2024] Onal, E. (2024). Computational game unit balancing. <https://github.com/emrek1/GameUnitBalancing>.
- [Patel et al., 2011] Patel, P., Carver, N., and Rahimi, S. (2011). Tuning computer gaming agents using q-learning. *2011 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS)*, pages 581–588.
- [Quiñones and Fernández, 2022] Quiñones, J. R. and Fernández, A. J. (2022). Automated video game parameter tuning with xvddl+. *J. Univers. Comput. Sci.*, 28:1282–1311.
- [Robinson, 1951] Robinson, J. (1951). An iterative method of solving a game. *Annals of mathematics*, pages 296–301.
- [Schreiber and Romero, 2021a] Schreiber, I. and Romero, B. (2021a). Game balance.
- [Schreiber and Romero, 2021b] Schreiber, I. and Romero, B. (2021b). Game balance. chapter 25, page 611. CRC Press.
- [Sironi and Winands, 2017] Sironi, C. F. and Winands, M. H. M. (2017). On-line parameter tuning for monte-carlo tree search in general game playing. In *CGW@IJCAI*.
- [Wang and Zhang, 2021] Wang, W. and Zhang, R. (2021). Improved game units balancing in game design through combinatorial optimization. *2021 IEEE International Conference on e-Business Engineering (ICEBE)*, pages 64–69.
- [Worden and Levin, 2007] Worden, L. and Levin, S. A. (2007). Evolutionary escape from the prisoner’s dilemma. *Journal of theoretical biology*, 245 3:411–22.

[Zook et al., 2019] Zook, A., Fruchter, E., and Riedl, M. O. (2019). Automatic playtesting for game parameter tuning via active learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.01417*.